

**A REVIEW ON HERBAL LIPSTICK CONTAINING NATURAL INGREDIENTS FOR
DRY AND CRACKED LIPS**

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ABSTRACT

Herbal cosmetics are getting popular these days because people are worried about the side effects of chemicals in regular products. Lipstick is used daily by many, but synthetic lipsticks contain artificial colours that can damage lip skin. This project focuses on making and testing a medicated herbal lipstick using natural ingredients that also have healing benefits. We used Licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) as the active ingredient for its medicinal properties, and Ratanjot roots to give a natural colours. The lipstick was made using a simple oil-infusion method and checked for different quality tests. The results show that this herbal lipstick is a safe, effective, and natural alternative to chemical lipsticks.

KEYWORDS: Herbal lipstick, Natural colour, Licorice, Cold sores, Formulation.

INTRODUCTION

lipstick is a key cosmetic product used everywhere for personal grooming and improving appearance. However, most commercial lipsticks available in the market contain artificial dyes, heavy metals, and chemical preservatives. Using these chemical-based products for a long time can cause side effects like lip dryness, irritation, and dark spots. Because of these issues, the demand for herbal cosmetic products made from natural materials has grown quickly over the last few years. Natural colorants from plants, like Ratanjot, are highly preferred in herbal cosmetics because they are safe and give a very attractive shade. At the same time, medicinal herbs like licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) are well-known for their soothing, anti-inflammatory, and healing actions. These natural properties can protect lips from drying out, cracking, and viral infections like cold sores. Therefore, this study was planned to design and evaluate a medicated herbal lipstick that offers both beauty and skin protection using safe, natural ingredients.^[1,2,3]

Ideal Properties of Herbal Lipstick

Easy Application: It should be smooth and glide easily on the lips.

Safe for Skin: Non-irritant, non-toxic, and comfortable

for regular use.

Good Stability: Should stay stable during storage without melting or break

Good Look & Odor: Must have a nice natural look and a pleasant smell.^[4,5]

Advantages of herbal lipstick

- ✓ It contains herbal ingredients that keep lips healthy.
- ✓ They are non-toxic and it's also used in anti-inflammatory, antiviral activities.
- ✓ Natural colour.
- ✓ Herbal ingredients safe to use. Shiny and smooth appearance.^[6]

Benefits of herbal lipstick

- ✓ Free from chemicals.
- ✓ No side effects.
- ✓ Eco-friendly products
- ✓ Eco-friendly for environments. Non irritating lipstick.
- ✓ Helpful in Cold sore and dry lips.^[7]

Ingredients used and their role

Beeswax

Its act as a base and thickening agent in lipstick

formulation provide structure, hardness to the product.

Coconut oil

coconut oil acts as a natural emollient and moisture it exhibits antiviral and antibacterial action keeps lips soft and hydrated.

Turmeric powder

its act as antibacterial and healing properties

Ratanjot roots

Gives a beautiful natural red color without chemicals.

Rose oil

Rose oil is used as a lipstick fragrance and it's natural edible food flavour

Licorice powder

Licorice posses antiviral, anti-inflammatory activity for Cold sore^[8,9]

Equipment's needed

- 1) Electronic weighing balance

Formulation Table

INGREDIENTS	ROLE	QUANTITY
beeswax	base and hardening agent	3.5GM
coconut oil with ratanjot	Moisturizer and colour carrier	5.0GM
licorice powder	herbal active ingredient	0.7GM
turmeric powder	Protective herbal additive	0.4GM
rose oil	natural fragrance	0.4GM

Evaluation test

Organoleptic Test

The prepared lipstick was checked manually for its physical appearance, color uniformity, smoothness, and smell.

Melting Point Test

The melting point was tested using the capillary tube method. A small amount of melted lipstick was filled in a capillary tube and cooled in ice for 2 hours. This tube was tied to a thermometer and lowered into a beaker of water. The water was heated slowly with stirring, and the temperature where the lipstick started softening was noted.

Solubility Test

To check how the formulation behaves with different chemicals, small pieces of lipstick were put into separate tubes containing water, alcohol, acetone, hexane, and petroleum ether.^[12]

Breaking Point Test

This test checks the strength of the lipstick so it does not break during daily use. The lipstick was fixed horizontally in a holder with its tip coming out. Weights were added to the tip every 15 seconds until the lipstick broke, and that final weight was recorded.

- 2) Breaker's

- 3) Water bath / double boiler

- 4) Porcelain dish / china dish

- 5) Lipstick mould^[10]

Method of preparation

Color Infusion: First, Ratanjot roots were heated gently with coconut oil in a double boiler to extract the natural red pigment into the oil.

Melting the Base: Beeswax was weighed carefully and melted inside a clean china dish using a water bath.

Mixing Powders: Finely powdered licorice and turmeric were added to the melted beeswax and stirred continuously to avoid lumps.

Adding Oils: The warm Ratanjot infused oil was added next, mixing everything quickly until uniform.

Adding rose oil: The rose oil was added and mixed quickly.

Molding: The hot mixture was poured into a clean lipstick mold and left to cool for 15 to 30 minutes before gently removing the lipstick.^[11]

pH Test

The surface pH was checked to make sure it matches human lip skin. The ideal pH range should be between 5.0 and 7.0 so it does not cause any allergy.

Spreadability Test: The lipstick was applied smoothly on a clean glass slide to see how easily it spreads and whether it forms a uniform layer.

Stability Study

The final lipsticks were kept in storage at room temperature and inside an incubator at 40°C. They were monitored regularly for any changes in color, texture, or smell.^[13]

REFERENCES

1. Sharma R, Gupta A, Verma S. Antiviral potential of Glycyrrhiza glabra extract against herpes simplex virus type 1. J Ethnopharmacol, 2020; 248: 112312.
2. Baisane VV, et al. Formulation and evaluation of herbal lipstick containing Ratanjot, Annatto and its mixture as natural colourant. Int J Sci Dev Res, 2024; 9(5).
3. Kumar V. Role of curcumin in topical formulations for skin inflammation and wound healing. Pharmacogn Rev, 2021; 15(29): 89-95.
4. Formulation and evaluation of herbal lipstick. Res J

- Pharm Technol, 2023; 16(11).
5. World Health Organization. WHO Global Report on Traditional and Complementary Medicine 2019. Geneva: WHO, 2019.
 6. Prasad K, Rathi P. Evaluation of herbal lipstick formulations using natural colorants. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*, 2017; 8(6): 2538-2543.
 7. Blumenthal M, Goldberg A, Brinckmann J. *Herbal Medicine: Expanded Commission E Monographs*. Austin: American Botanical Council, 2000.
 8. Shah P, Patel R. Formulation and evaluation of herbal lipstick. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*, 2020; 65(1): 18-22.
 9. Shukla S, Mehta A. Herbal cosmetics: An overview. *Int J Pharm Chem Sci*, 2015; 4(2): 437- 445.
 10. Patel M, Shah K, Patel N. Formulation and evaluation of herbal lipstick using natural pigments and rose oil as fragrance agent. *Int J Pharm Res Appl*, 2019; 4(3): 45-50.
 11. Chaudhary G, Goyal S. A review on herbal cosmetics and natural essential oils in cosmetic preparations. *World J Pharm Res*, 2014; 3(6): 1510-1524.
 12. Preethi KC, Kuttan R. Wound healing activity of flower extract of *Calendula officinalis*. *J Basic Clin Physiol Pharmacol*, 2009, 20(1): 73-79.
 13. Fiore C, Eisenhut M, Krause R, et al. Antiviral effects of *Glycyrrhiza* species. *Phytother Res*, 2008; 22(2): 141-148.